

Review Article

Evaluation And Preparation of Herbal Hair Oil

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ABSTRACT

Hair plays an important role in human behavior. We use many cosmetics to improve our hair. Herbal preparations always work, they have little or no side effects compared to synthetic products. This study focuses on the importance of herbal hair oil in treating hair problems such as baldness, alopecia, hair loss, gray hair, dryness and dandruff in general. Herbal hair oil is designed to treat hair. Herbal hair oil not only moisturizes the scalp but also reverses the condition of dry scalp and hair. It provides many essential nutrients necessary to maintain the activity of the sebaceous glands and promote natural hair growth. The aim of the current study was to prepare and analyze various hair oils containing medicinal herbs. All these drugs have a well-known drug potential in hair treatment. Herbal hair oil provides great benefits to hair. Herbal hair oil contains vitamins and micronutrients that act as nutrients for your hair.

Herbal hair oil obtained from natural sources. Restores vitality to hair tissue. However, your shampoo and conditioner contain many good ingredients, but they do not care for your scalp as deeply as hair oil. Regular use of herbal hair remedies can treat premature graying of hair.

INTRODUCTION

Various herbs used in the recipe include amla, banyan root, onion, brahmi, aloe vera, fenugreek seeds, mallow, curry leaves, coconut oil. All ingredients provide essential nutrients such as vitamins, antioxidants, proteins, terpenoids and many essential oils to maintain the activity of the sebaceous glands. Herbal hair oil not only moisturizes the scalp, but also heals the scalp and dry hair. The formulated oil has beneficial

properties, acid value, saponification value, viscosity, pH, etc. is evaluated in terms of All parameters are good and comply with standards. This is an ancient method as it is found in the historical Vedas and Unani. Chemical hair oils are called conditioners.

This herb has always attracted the attention of beauty due to its powerful properties and has little to no impact on synthetic chemicals. Emblica emblica is rich in vitamin C, tannins and minerals

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such as phosphorus, iron and calcium, which provide nutrients to the hair and also cause hair to turn black. Hibiscus contains calcium. Phosphorus, Iron, Vitamin B1, Riboflavin, Niacin and Vitamin C are used to support thick hair and prevent premature hair loss. Brahmi contains alkaloids that increase protein kinase activity. Fenugreek (Methi) seeds are rich in protein, which provides the necessary protein for hair. Banana roots contain carbohydrates, flavonoids, amino acids/proteins, steroids, saponins and tannins solves the problem of hair loss and breakage. Aloe vera is rich in glycosides, amino acids, resins, vitamins and minerals, making hair better, shinier and softer. Curry leaves contain organic compounds and alkaloids, flavonoids, carbohydrates and sterol products that coat the hair and make it shiny. Coconut oil is rich in saturated fatty acid triglycerides that improve hair and scalp health. Mekaa (Mehendi) Contains 0.2-0.3% alkaloids to strengthen hair. Onion contains quercetin, quercetin-3-glycoside, fructose, flavonoids, sulfur, organosulfur compounds that support hair follicles and reduce hair breakage and thinning.

Ingredients :

1. Curry Leaves :

Biological source: Dried leaves of *Murrayakoenigii*

Family: Rutaceae

Use: Prevents the hairfall and early greying of hair.

2. Amla :

Biological source: Dried fruits of *phyllanthus Emblica*

Family: Phyllanthaceae

Use: hair conditioner, treats scalp ailments, helps hair growth.

3. Coconut oil :

Biological source: Oil derived from dried fruits of *Cocusnucifera*.

Family: Arecaceae.

Use: moisturiser, vehicle, motivates hair growth by releasing pores.

4. Aloe vera :

Biological source: aloe is the dried juice collected by incision from the bases of the leaves of various species of *Aloe Barbadensis*.

Family: Asphodelaceae

Use: It also acts as a great conditioner and leaves your hair all smooth and shiny. It promotes is the hair growth, prevents of the itching on the scalp, reduces dandruff and conditions your hair.

5. Parijat :

Biological source : *Nyctanthus arbortrisis* Linn.

Family: oleaceae

Use: relief from hair fall Juice of Parijat flower or paste of the seeds, when applied to the scalp, can give the quick results and also promote hair growth.

6. Brahmi :

Biological source: Brahmi is consist of the fresh and dried leaves and stem of *Centella asiatica* Linn.

Family: scrophulariaceae

Use: removes dryness, longing and cracking

7. Tulsi:

Biological source: *Ocimum tenuiflorum*

Family: lamiaceae

Use: strengthen hire strands and the prevent hair loss

8. Onion

Family: Amaryllidaceae

Use: It reduce hair loss by cultivating blood circulation in the scalp and hair. The sulphur in the juice helps in the production of the essential collagen that promotes hair growth.

9. Fenugreek seeds :

Biological source: Fenugreek is derived from dried seeds of *Trigonella foenum graceum*

Family: fabaceae

Uses: recovers damaged hair, controls scalp inflammation, adds shine and soft texture

10. Hibiscus:

Biological source: hibiscus is derived from dried flower of hibiscus *Rosa sinensis*

Family: malvaceae

Use: improve hair growth, cures dandruff and itchiness, prevent premature greyness.

Procedure:

The process followed in the preparation of various herbal hair tonics. The following steps are involved in the preparation of various herbal hair tonics. One two. Prepare Coconut Oil Base Boil the crude medicine powder in coconut oil base to make a concentrated hair growth agent. Coconut oil is extracted from the kernel by drying, completing the process of extracting coconut oil from dry seeds mentioned above. It is used and stored as oil based. The crude drug is based on the following. i) Collection of crude medicine: Collection of crude medicine of neem, mallow, eclipta and amla. ii) Drying of Crude Drugs: Crude drugs are dried in a cool place and proper ventilation is provided to accelerate the drying process. Dry in a cool place to preserve the active ingredients. Therefore freeze drying is better than dry drying. iii) Mixing and mixing of dry chemical products: Use equipment to grind dry chemical products into coarse powder. After that, all the coarse powder was passed through an 80-mesh sieve. The resulting powder is mixed separately to obtain a homogeneous mixture. iv) Preparation of herbal hair tonic: Use pure coconut oil obtained from coconut. Initially, the oil is heated above a low temperature. It's hot Get the necessary oils and

medicines and use bandages to hold them. Dip the healing mixture inside the muslin cloth into hot oil. Continue the process by placing the fabric in and out of hot coconut oil over low heat. In this way, the active ingredients of the crude drug are absorbed into the hot coconut oil. The hot oil is then cooled and processed to remove bacteria from the starch. At first the oil will be brown. After the crude oil is kept in a cold place for a week, its color will turn light green. v) Product Packaging: This oil has a pleasant scent and has hair growth promoting activity. Hair oil is a product prepared entirely from natural ingredients, has no side effects and has great benefits. It comes in an amber bottle and is sealed. The bottle is then sealed in an airtight bottle. vi) Store multi-purpose hair: Store in a closed bottle, in the refrigerator. This allows the oil to remain stable for longer without rancidity or saponification.

Formulation:

Preparation of Compound Hair Oil All raw materials are made from chemical products and dried in the shade. Dry in a cool place to preserve the active ingredients. Therefore, drying in the shade is better than drying. Use a spoon to grind the dry powder into a coarse powder. Then, all coarse powdered substances were sieved through an 80-mesh sieve and the powders were mixed to obtain a homogeneous mixture. Now add coconut oil and aloe vera pulp. These are all dry powders. Now boil the contents for 15 minutes and strain through cheesecloth. To filter, add coconut oil to increase volume. Finally, prepare a multi-purpose hair oil. These come in amber colored bottles.

Formulation Table:

Sr. No.	Ingredients	Quantity
1.	Curry Leaves	8 gm
2.	Amla	10 gm
3.	Coconut Oil	40 ml
4.	Aloe Vera	3 gm
5.	Parijat	1 gm
6.	Brahmi	1 gm
7.	Tulsi	1 gm

8.	Onion	10 gm
9.	Fenugreek Seeds	3.5 gm
10.	Hibiscus	3 gm

Collection of crude drug:

Collect crude medicine:

- i. Collect crude medicine from hibiscus, and amla.
- ii. **Drying of Crude Oil:** The crude oil is dried in a cool place and proper ventilation is provided to accelerate the drying process. Dry in a cool place to preserve the active ingredients. Therefore freeze drying is better than dry drying.
- iii. **Mixing and blending of dry chemical ingredients:** Use a machine to grind the dry chemical ingredients into a coarse powder. After that, all the coarse powder was passed through an 80-mesh sieve. The resulting powder is mixed separately to obtain a homogeneous mixture.
- iv. **Preparation of herbal hair tonic:** Use pure coconut oil obtained from coconut. Initially, the oil is heated above a low temperature. Take the crude medicine, which should be in a cheesecloth, and add it to this hot oil. Dip the healing mixture inside the muslin cloth into hot oil. Continue the process by placing the fabric in and out of hot coconut oil over low heat. In this way, the active ingredients of the crude drug are absorbed into the hot coconut oil. The hot oil is then cooled and processed to remove bacteria from the starch. At first the oil will be brown. After the crude oil is kept in a cold place for a week, its color will turn light green.
- v. **Product Packaging:** This oil has a pleasant scent and has hair growth promoting activity. Hair oil is a product prepared entirely from natural ingredients, has no side effects and has great benefits. It comes in an amber bottle and is sealed. The bottle is then sealed in an airtight bottle.

- vi. **Store multi-purpose hair:** Store in a closed bottle, in the refrigerator. This allows the oil to remain stable for longer without rancidity or saponification.

Evaluation of herbal hair oil:

Vegetable oil was evaluated in terms of parameters such as pH value, acid value, saponification value, negative index, viscosity and index 9 and 10.

1. **Acid value:** Add 25ml ethanol and 25ml ether to 10ml oil. Add phenolphthalein as indicator and titrate with 0.1 M potassium hydroxide solution,

$$\text{acid value} = 5.61n/w \text{ where,}$$

$$n = \text{ml of 0.1M KOH}$$

$$>> w = \text{weight oil}$$

2. **Saponification rate:** Weigh 2 g of oil and transfer it to a 250 ml iodine bottle. Add 25 ml of 0.5M potassium hydroxide alcohol, reflux and boil in a water bath for

30 minutes. Add phenolphthalein as indicator and titrate with 0.5M HCl ("a" ml). Similarly, a blank ("b" ml) was prepared without sample. Saponification rate: $28.05(b-a)/w$ Where, **w** = weight (in grams) of solution.

3. **pH:** Test the pH of the vegetable oil using a pH meter.

4. **Viscosity:** Viscosity is measured using an Ostwald viscometer.

5. **Specific Gravity:** Use a pycnometer or pycnometer to determine the specific gravity of the prepared oil.

6. **Refractive index:** measured with a refractometer.

7. **Sensory properties:** colour, odor, skin irritation are determined manually. Apply the oil to your hands and leave it in the sun for 5 minutes, check for skin irritation.

CONCLUSION

Herbal hair oil is one of the most well-known hair care products. Herbal hair oil not only moisturizes the scalp but also reverses dry scalp and dry hair conditions. It provides many important nutrients

needed to maintain the activity of the sebaceous glands and promote hair growth. Herbal hair oil is made from various herbs. Their importance in the formula Many parameters such as sensitivity test, viscosity, pH, irritation test, sand test, saponification were evaluated and the acid value of the herbal hair oil. Therefore, from the current research formulated herbal hair oil has been found to have good structure and attachment structure and biological analysis has identified the reason why herbal hair oil is good.

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